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Role of Heroines in the Shakespearean Plays

Sanjai Kumar,
Research Scholar (English)
Singhania University,
Pachheri Bari,
Jhunjhunu, (Rajasthan)

Suman Singh
Asst. Professor (English)
P.P.N. College,
Kanpur, (U.P.)

Abstract

John Ruskin has said, "Shakespeare has no hero, but heroine". This statement that Shakespeare has no hero, but heroines aptly fits on his comedies. In his great tragedies like 'Macbeth', 'King Lear', 'Hamlet' and 'Othello'. I find male characters equally important. But there are also female characters like Lady Macbeth and Cordellia who played very important role. But in comedies we find only female characters dominating the stage. The fine comedies like 'Twelfth Night', 'As You Like It', 'A Mid Summer Night's Dream' and 'Tempest' have a galaxy of "Queens of beauty intellect, wisdom and of resolution and determination". Shakespeare's heroines are guided by intuitive (modest) insight at the time of crisis. Naturally his heroines are more sympathetic than men. They earn goodwill much quicker than do men. Also people get more interested in their affairs than in those of men. His heroines are always elevating and inspiring. Dr. Protima Tagore has said "Shakespeare's kingdom of dramatic art has no kings but only queens." Undoubtedly it feels that it is a reality. I think that Shakespeare is a great master of human psychology and had penetrated deeper into feminine psychology and studied thoroughly, the mind and soul of woman, and found in her something, noble and sublime than in man. His heroines are quick, active and full of enthusiasm. They are whole and graceful. They are adventurous and with clear insight. These heroines of Shakespeare's brighter comedies are "Voyagers in pursuit of happiness, not yet attained- a Brave New world, wherein man's life may be fuller, his sensations more exquisite, and his joys more widespread more lasting and so, more humane." They are more for the happiness of others than their own. They strive to procure greatest happiness of all those whom they come across. They set as pace-makers and match-makers. His heroines play a vital role in uniting the lovers in the end. It is because of the heroine in the Twelfth Night that three weddings take place when the curtain drop and all bitterness is banished. Although there has been a lot of work on this topic, I hope my paper would facilitate the understanding of the scholars.

Keywords: Important, enthusiasm, inspiring, affection, intuition, favourite, adventurous & crisis

Introduction

Shakespeare found women more sensitive to intuition and more responsive to emotion. They had a fine instinct of mother-wit, a variety of humanized common sense. They are full of human feelings. Shakespeare has made woman not only heroine of his comedy, but of the entire realm of reason, intellect and of returning affection. They have the gift of inspiring and of returning affection. They have the good will of all who know them. They are simply human and natural in their response to emotional crisis like that of falling in love.

Naturally Shakespeare's heroines are more sympathetic than men. They earn goodwill much quicker than do men. Also people get more interested in their affairs than in those of men. They are guided by modest insight at the time of crises which I see in Tempest, Othello, Macbeth, Merchant of Venice, Julius Caesar & Romeo and Juliet etc.

So I would like to say something about some heroines who played a very important role in the Shakespearean plays due to which John Ruskin (8 Feb.1819 – 20 Jan.1900 England, London), who was the leading English art critic of the Victorian era, also an art patron, draughtsman, watercolorist, a prominent social thinker and philanthropist has said, "Shakespeare has no hero, but heroine".

His statement that Shakespeare has no hero, but heroines aptly fits on his comedies. In comedies we find only female characters dominating the stage. The fine comedies like 'Twelfth Night', 'As You Like

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It, 'A Mid Summer Night's Dream' and 'Tempest' have a galaxy of "Queens of beauty intellect, wisdom and of resolution and determination".

Dr. Protima Tagore (1893-1969), writer of the famous books titled 'Nirvan', 'Nriya' and 'Shrutilekha' who belongs to the Tagore family and assisted Rabindranath Tagore in the production of dance, dramas and plays, has said, "Shakespeare's kingdom of dramatic art has no kings but only queens." Undoubtedly it feels that it is a reality, in comedies.

In his great tragedies, like 'Macbeth', 'King Lear', 'Hamlet' and 'Othello' I find male characters equally important. But there are also female characters like Lady Macbeth and Cordelia who played very important role. Shakespeare allows his heroines more freedom to explore their sexuality, perhaps because their low-status renders them social harmlessness. They are adventurous and with clear insight. Regarding these heroines of Shakespeare's brighter comedies are, as a critic has said: "Voyagers in pursuit of happiness, not yet attained- a Brave New world, wherein man's life may be fuller, his sensations more exquisite, and his joys more widespread more lasting and so, more humane."

High-born women are presented as "possessions" to be passed between fathers and husbands. In most cases, they are socially restricted and unable to explore the world around them without chaperones. These women were coerced and controlled by the men in their lives. Broadly speaking, female characters that sexually aware are more likely to be lower class. Shakespeare allows them more freedom to explore their sexuality, perhaps because their low-status renders them socially harmless. However, women are never totally free in Shakespeare's plays: if not owned by husbands and fathers, many low class characters are owned by their employers.

Although to discuss about all the heroines or women characters in the Shakespearean play is very difficult task, but a few things about a few heroine characters may said briefly, so I would like to say something about the following heroines who played very important role in the Shakespearean plays. I would like to give some of the examples of women i.e. heroines of Shakespeare to show their characteristics and qualities how they are more different than heroes due to why it is said that Shakespeare has no hero but heroin. Some of the notable women characters are as follows:

Viola, in Twelfth Night

Let us take up the case of a great heroine Viola in Twelfth Night. We find her in the very beginning of the drama in distress. But she is not all nervous. She is brave enough to face the furies of the foaming fierce sea. She survives the calamity. She takes a bold step in taking up serve either with the countess or with the Duke and that too in disguise. She has all courtly qualities and manners. She has that quality in her which makes her favourite of every one. First the sea-captain promises her all sort of help. When she reaches in the Court of Duke Orsino she wins his favour and confidence within no time. She is being assigned a new and very important task

of winning over the love of countess in favour of Duke. Duke has all praises for her.

Beatrice, in Much Ado About Nothing

Beatrice is Leonato's niece, Hero's cousin, and the sworn enemy/true love of Benedick. While she's supposed to be billed a best supporting actress, it's usually agreed that she tends to steal the show. Her wit and her candor, combined with her vulnerability, arguably make her the play's most fleshed out (and endearing) character. We know she feels deeply, is smart, and able enough to transfer her feelings into their appropriate outlets, whether good humor or anger. Like Rosalind, Beatrice is self-aware enough to realize she's fallen victim to love. But unlike Rosalind, she can't bring herself to use her wit to mock her own situation. Beatrice, more than any character in this play displays the realistic characteristics of a brilliant woman in love. She's afraid to be vulnerable, she's scornful of being a wimpy, lovesick fool, and all of these characteristics combine make her hesitant to dive into a romance headfirst. In this way, unlike Hero, who gives over her love like an obedient girl, Beatrice is a wise and warm woman. She is defended by her wit only up to a point, but when the time comes for love, she's self-aware and realistic enough to realize that she just has to take the risk and hope for the best.

Cleopatra, in Antony and Cleopatra

Many people consider the role of Cleopatra in this play, as one of the most complex female roles in Shakespeare's work. She is frequently vain and histrionic, provoking an audience almost to scorn; at the same time, Shakespeare's efforts invest both her and Antony with tragic grandeur. These contradictory features have led to famously divided critical responses.

Cordelia, in King Lear

Cordelia is a fictional character in William Shakespeare's tragic play, King Lear. She is the youngest of King Lear's three daughters. After her elderly father offers her the opportunity to profess her love to him in return for one third of the land in his kingdom, she refuses and is banished for the majority of the play. Cordelia is Lear's favorite daughter and is often compared to a Cinderella character. After Lear is rejected by Goneril and Regan, the wicked sisters, he goes mad. Cordelia returns at the end of the play with the intentions of helping him, ultimately reversing her role as daughter to mother. But when she arrives, he doesn't even recognize her. Nevertheless, she forgives him for banishing her. By the time Lear finally regains his reason and realizes who Cordelia is, they have little time to talk and reconcile; Edmund arrives and sends them to prison, where Cordelia is ultimately hanged. In a revision which replaced the original on stage for decades, Nahum Tate's, The History of King Lear (1681) Cordelia marries Edgar and becomes ruler of the kingdom.

Cressida, in Troilus and Cressida

Daughter of the soothsayer Calchas. Troilus successfully woos her but discovers later that she is fickle and lascivious. Although callow Troilus loses his love, he fails to realize she was a wanton to begin with. Moreover, he does not die or experience a moment of epiphany. Hector dies, but he is neither a

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title character nor a character whose psyche and personality undergo thorough examination. Fickle Cressida, forcibly separated from Troilus, does not resist the Greeks. In fact, she welcomes their attentions, in particular those of Diomedes. She is anything but tragically heroic.

Desdemona, in Othello

Shakespeare's Desdemona is a Venetian beauty who enrages and disappoints her father, a Venetian senator, when she elopes with Othello, a man several years her senior. When her husband is deployed to Cyprus in the service of the Republic of Venice, Desdemona accompanies him. There, her husband is manipulated by his ensign Iago into believing she is an adulteress, and, in the last act, she is murdered by her estranged spouse. By marrying Othello, Desdemona defies both parental authority and the social convention of her times. There is no doubt that this is also a racial thing. Her father Brabantio laments:

It is too true an evil: gone she is;
And what's to come of my despised time
Is nought but bitterness. Now, Roderigo,
Where didst thou see her? O unhappy girl!

Goneril, in King Lear

Goneril is one of Lear's wicked daughters. After Lear gives her half his lands, she promptly betrays him and doesn't shed a tear when Lear is forced to wander, homeless and exposed to the elements of nature. Because Goneril ends up doing such evil things – including poisoning her own sister over an evil philanderer – it's easy to just label her "the wicked daughter" and be done. But both Regan and Goneril are more complex than that, especially when you argue that they start out with good reason to be upset with Lear. Speaking of suicide, let's check out Goneril's death. We've already established that she's a pretty awful person, so what would make her kill herself? It's a rather easy, cop-out answer to say that she feels guilty about poisoning Regan, but that's rather contrary to her character. In all likelihood, Regan is going to have to face trial or possibly get murdered by a vengeance-crazed man. Goneril, being Goneril, would rather die than apologize, so she kills herself.

Hermia, in A Midsummer Night's Dream

Shakespeare introduces Hermia to us as the disobedient daughter of Egeus. She's supposed to marry Demetrius, but she's fallen in love with Lysander. Hermia could be mistaken for being young and foolish in love, but actually the whole thing is put in perspective by the fact that her father wants her killed (a standard punishment under Athenian law for disobeying one's father, apparently). She's been brought before Duke Theseus because of her father's complaint, and under these circumstances, she's pretty bold to stand up for herself. Hermia doesn't want to marry Demetrius because she's true to her love. Her boldness is a little reminiscent of that favorite Shakespeare heroine, Rosalind in *As You Like It*. Like Rosalind, Hermia is no fool, and though she realizes that men break promises, she's willing to take a chance and run off with Lysander anyway.

Hero, in Much Ado About Nothing

Hero is Leonato's daughter, Beatrice's cousin, Antonio's niece, and the beloved (and slandered) fiancée of Claudio. She's a gentle, loving girl who doesn't have much of a backbone, but doesn't have much of a mean-streak either. Though she is supposed to be the female lead of the play, Hero has the fewest lines of the four primary characters. Her defining characteristic is that she's always reacting to the actions and commands of others, and is rarely the agent of action herself interestingly. Hero is the idyllic version of a sweet and innocent girl who is wronged in love, but somehow finds the power to overcome that wrong and love again. She isn't vulnerable emotionally, just vulnerable to circumstance. Besides her sweetness (and her willingness to roll over when commanded), she doesn't have many distinguishing characteristics. She is not fully fleshed out, and though we hear of her apprehension about getting married, we don't ever hear any of her intense personal struggles or challenges. As a result, Hero's character ends up being a bit of a one-dimensional good girl.

Imogen, in Cymbeline

Imogen was the daughter of King Cymbeline in Shakespeare's play *Cymbeline*. She was described by William Hazlitt as "perhaps the most tender and the most artless" of all Shakespeare's women. Imogen is princess of Britain, and the virtuous wife of the exiled Posthumus, whose praise of her moral purity incites Posthumus's acquaintance Iachimo to bet Posthumus that he can seduce her. After the battle at the climax of the play she confronts Iachimo who confesses his lies. She is reunited with Posthumus, her father (King Cymbeline), and discovers two of the men who took her in are actually her long lost brothers.

Isabella, in Measure for Measure

The most important thing to know about Isabella is that she's a virgin and she plans on staying that way forever. We wonder why Isabella wants to lead such an extreme lifestyle. Is it simply because our girl wants a closer relationship with God, or is there more to it?

Rosalind, in As You Like It

Rosalind is a fictional character and the romantic female lead in the play *'As You Like It'*. She is the daughter of the exiled Duke Senior and niece to his usurping brother Duke Frederick and a beautiful cousin of Celia (usurper's daughter). Her father is banished from the kingdom which breaks her heart. She then meets Orlando and falls in love with him. After angering her uncle, she leaves his court for exile in the Forest of Arden. There, she lives disguised as a shepherd named Ganymede with her devoted cousin, Celia disguised as his sister, Aliena and her uncle's fool Touchstone. Eventually, Rosalind is reunited with her father and is married to her faithful lover, Orlando. Rosalind is one of Shakespeare's most recognized heroines. Her true decision-making skills can be seen in the last act of Scene V where she has to present herself as Rosalind to her father and to Orlando, but at the same time change Phebe's opinion to marry Silvius. She is the main character of the play who

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extracts the clarity of important traits in other characters.

Olivia, in Twelfth Night

At first, Olivia seems to be the emotional counterpart for the duke; he is a melancholy parallel for Olivia, and Olivia has sworn to abjure the world for seven years to mourn for her dead brother, an act of extreme sentimental melancholy. Olivia is also the opposite of Viola in many ways. But later she is presented as being essentially an intelligent woman with a number of good qualities. Her intelligence is constantly seen in the many household matters that she has to attend to. While she recognizes the duke's good qualities and acknowledges them, she is adamant in her refusals, and, thus, it is part of the comedy that the lady who has no sympathy for the duke falls so irrationally in love with a young girl disguised as a young boy. When she discovers that she has actually married young Sebastian, Viola's twin, she quickly transfers her love to him, just as Duke Orsino is able to transfer his love to Viola.

Portia, in the Merchant of Venice

A wealthy heiress from Belmont. Portia's beauty is matched only by her intelligence. Bound by a clause in her father's will that forces her to marry whichever suitor chooses correctly among three caskets, Portia is nonetheless able to marry her true love, Bassanio. Far and away the cleverest of the play's characters, it is Portia, in the disguise of a young law clerk, who saves Antonio from Shylock's knife.

Conclusion

Finally, I would like to say that Shakespeare is a great master of human psychology and had penetrated deeper into feminine psychology. He studied thoroughly, the mind and soul of woman, and found in them something, noble and sublime than in men. Shakespeare's women have questionable morals. Women in power are treated with distrust by Shakespeare. For example, Gertrude in Hamlet marries her husband's murdering brother and Lady Macbeth forces her husband into murder. For these women, the penalty for their scheming ways is normally death. High-born women are presented as "possessions" to be passed between fathers and husbands.

In most cases, they are socially restricted and unable to explore the world around them without chaperones. His heroines are elevating and inspiring. His heroines are quick, active and full of enthusiasm. They are whole and graceful. They are courageous and with clear insight. Shakespeare found women more sensitive to intuition and more responsive to emotion. They had a fine instinct of mother-wit, a variety of humanized common sense. They are full of human feelings. Shakespeare has made woman not only heroine of his comedy, but of the entire realm of reason, intellect and self-sacrifice. They are quick, active and full of enthusiasm. They are whole and graceful. They are courageous and with clear insight. They have the gift of inspiring and of returning affection. They are simply human and patently natural in their response to emotional crisis like that of falling in love. They are more for the happiness of others than their own. They strive to procure greatest

happiness of all those whom they come across. They set as pace-makers and match-makers. His heroines play a vital role in uniting the lovers in the end which we may see in As You like It & Othello etc. They have the good will of all who know them. They are simply human and patently natural in their response to emotional crisis like that of falling in love.

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